

8T – The Trajectory of a Particle

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main two equations of the new 8T framework, the author will try to answer the question of calculating the trajectory of a particle on a varying manifold with (3,1) signature that was invoked stationary by EL operator. Author in addition will provide a take on whether such questions are necessary in a final theory of physics.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard fermions and in particular quarks as arbitrary variations of a manifold which vanish into matter. The process of vanishing ensuring that no curvature is allowed. The exclusion of curvature yielding than the group suggested by Gell-Mann in the 20-th century. That is described by the main equation that describes a varying Lorentz manifold, which was invoked stationary:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Allowing it to experience arbitrary amounts of curvature, we have proven the existence of Quarks:

$$\left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

That was by discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.1), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements which differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The following procedure was presented in the thesis, given only four elements in the series and one of the pluses varied to a minus.

$$O: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_1 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination.

$$\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$$

Since, we have a threefold combination that will pair the inverse in sign; so the both would vanish into zero. Thus, we can consider the total charge of the threefold combination to be an integer and its inverse:

$$\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(O)\delta g_1 \Leftrightarrow \delta g_2(O)\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2$$

Suppose we have a particle, or a threefold combination of two distinct elements. Is it possible to derive the path in which it will choose? What kind of information is needed to answer such a question? The answer is vividly clear; to know and calculate the trajectory of the particle we will need the distribution of net curvature on the metric tensor. In other words, the distributions of bosonic ripples across the manifold. Those ripples are as you already know, isomorphic to primes or one, given by the coupling mathematical series:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.3}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.31}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.32}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

The key point to this short essay, is that the appearance of those net curvatures across the metric tensor is completely random, there is no reasoning or logic behind it. The configuration of the metric tensor is than varying in ways which not predictable and so it is impossible to answer questions regarding the motion of the particle in such framework. To answer such questions we need a space time which is static in a sense or variations. In QFT terms we say that no fluctuations are allowed. The difference is that in 8T the Quantum fluctuations of the vacuum are metric tensor perturbations vanishing into matter in even numbers, or diverge across the manifold as net curvature as bosonic fields if prime number or one – as a short range.

One final point, even if we would answer such question, and that is a take regarding the kind of questions that were asked in 20-th century before QM, even if somehow it was possible to calculate the trajectory of all particles, what kind of understanding would we gain? Those questions according to ones views are not part of a final theory, as they are calculation oriented not understating oriented. The 8T was built upon questions of the second orientation and as a result have two strong equations that unified curvature settings with QM and not a single calculation in it (other than the coupling constants series). Good theory is built upon first and foremost, good questions. If the primordial coupling series is considered an important equation, than the questions we should emphasize in a physical theory should be oriented to understanding and not to calculation.

References

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